
Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS)

Instructions and Documentation

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Introduction

The Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS) are a self-assessment tool for exploring how resilient a data repository may be during normal operations and in times of crisis. Whether you are a repository manager, data user, citizen archivist, community partner, or someone familiar with a repository, the RCS gives you a structured way to identify where the repository is well prepared and where there may be gaps that need attention.

The RCS evaluates repositories across seven areas, covering everything from how data are stored and documented to how well the repository could respond to a natural disaster, cyberattack, loss of critical staff, or loss of funding. After completing the assessment, respondents receive a report with an overall resilience score, individual scores for each of the seven areas, readiness scores for four specific crisis scenarios, and prioritized recommendations for improvement.

The purpose of the RCS is to support reflection, planning, and discussion. The RCS is not intended to serve as a formal audit, certification, ranking, or external evaluation.

How to Complete the RCS

The RCS is available in the following formats:

- [Online Form](#) (*preferred*) - The form version includes automatic scoring and generates a report upon completion. Responses are anonymous and help us understand how the RCS is being used across the community.
- [Google Sheets Version](#) - A spreadsheet version with built-in scoring. Requires a Google login.
- [Excel Spreadsheet \(.xlsx\)](#) - A spreadsheet version with built-in scoring for offline use. Available for download on Zenodo.
- [PDF or Word Document \(.docx\)](#) - Useful for reference, to preview the questions or gather responses from your team before entering them into the online form. Available for download on Zenodo.

For each statement in the assessment, select the response that best reflects the repositories current practices using the following scale:

Score	Response	Meaning
1	Not in place	No practice, plan, or capability exists.
2	Limited / ad hoc	Informal or inconsistent; depends on individual effort.
3	Partially in place	Exists in some form but incomplete or untested.
4	Mostly in place	Largely implemented; minor gaps remain
5	Fully in place	Comprehensive, documented, and regularly verified.
N/A	Not applicable	This question does not apply to the repository. Use sparingly - see guidance below.

Be as honest as possible when rating the repository practices. The RCS is most useful when it reflects reality rather than aspiration. If you are unsure about a response, select the rating that best describes the current state, not where you hope to be.

Using N/A. The N/A option is available for questions that genuinely do not apply to your repository. However, it should be used sparingly. Most questions are designed to be relevant to all repository types. If more than half of the questions in any section are marked N/A, that section will be flagged as having insufficient data for a reliable score and will be excluded from reporting. If you find yourself marking many questions as N/A, it is worth pausing to consider whether those practices truly do not apply, or whether they simply have not been addressed yet.

Who should complete it? The RCS may be completed individually or as a group. Some users may be able to answer most questions on their own, while others may benefit from completing the RCS with colleagues or partners who understand different aspects of repository operations. The RCS can also be retaken over time as conditions change, improvements are implemented, or priorities shift.

Multiple repositories? If your organization is responsible for more than one repository or program (for example, managing both a general data archive and a specialized project collection) complete the assessment separately for each one. Scores from different repositories should not be combined.

Seven Sections of the RCS

The RCS is organized into seven sections, each addressing a distinct area of repository resilience. Together, they cover the full range of practices that determine how well a repository can withstand and recover from disruption.

Here is a brief overview of what each section covers and why it matters:

A - Data Stewardship (10 questions)

This section looks at how well your data is protected, replicated, and documented. It asks whether your data exists in multiple independent locations, whether it is stored in ways that would survive a single point of failure, and whether it is described well enough for others to find and use it if needed. Strong data stewardship is the foundation of resilience. Without well-protected and well-documented data, no other practice can prevent permanent loss.

B - Infrastructure & Staffing (6 questions)

This section examines the resilience of your physical infrastructure and your people. It asks whether your facilities have backup power and systems, whether your team is cross-trained so that no single person is a critical dependency, and whether you have plans in place for leadership transitions. Operational resilience depends as much on your people and facilities as it does on your technology.

C - Software (3 questions)

This section evaluates whether your software environment would hold up in a crisis. It asks whether your data can be accessed without proprietary tools, whether your software is open, well-maintained, and documented well enough for someone new to set it up. Software is generally more recoverable than lost data, but poor software practices can significantly slow down recovery.

D - Cybersecurity & Access Control (3 questions)

This section looks at how well your systems and data are protected from unauthorized access, accidental deletion, and malicious activity. It asks whether activity is logged and monitored, whether access permissions are appropriately restricted, and whether qualified cybersecurity expertise is available to you. Cyber threats can have immediate and irreversible consequences, making this area a high-priority focus.

E - Crisis Response & Recovery (11 questions)

This is the largest section and the most directly relevant to the tool's core purpose. It asks whether your repository has the plans, capabilities, and documentation needed to respond effectively when a crisis actually happens; from remote work capability and data transfer options to disaster recovery planning and dependency mapping. A repository may have strong practices in other areas but still be unprepared if it has not thought through how it would actually respond.

F - Networks, Partnerships & Community (3 questions)

This section looks at the relationships your repository has with external and internal partners. It asks whether you have formal agreements for data or operational support in a crisis, and whether your user community and stakeholders are engaged in resilience planning. Strong partnerships mean you are not facing a crisis alone. Pre-established agreements and relationships can be activated quickly when they are needed most.

G - Sustainability & Continuity (6 questions)

This section examines your repository's long-term viability. It asks whether your funding is diversified, whether you have plans for migrating data to new formats over time, and whether formal agreements are in place to ensure your holdings are preserved if your repository can no longer operate. Resilience is not just about surviving a crisis today, it is about ensuring your data remains accessible for the long term.

The Four Crisis Scenarios

In addition to measuring your repository's general resilience practices, the RCS maps each question to one or more of four crisis scenarios. This allows you to determine not just how your practices compare across sections, but how well-prepared you are for specific types of disruption.

Each scenario score is calculated using only the questions most relevant to that crisis. This means a repository could score well overall but have a specific vulnerability to one type of crisis, or vice versa. The scenario scores are designed to surface exactly those kinds of nuances.

Natural Disaster in 48 Hours

A natural disaster such as a hurricane or wildfire is forecasted to strike your primary facility within 48 hours. The area is expected to suffer significant damage, requiring full evacuation of the facility (including all physical devices and storage) with no clear timeline for when the facility might be restored.

This scenario tests whether your data exists in locations that would survive the loss of your primary site, whether your team can operate remotely, and whether you have the plans and procedures in place to respond quickly. The focus is on physical resilience, geographic distribution of data, and rapid response capability.

Loss of Funding / Defunding

Your repository has been informed that its primary funding source is ending. You need to either find alternative funding or plan for the transition of your data to another home. The scenario assumes that the funding loss is total (eventually affecting staff, hardware, and software) but that there is some time available to take mitigating action before operations cease entirely.

This scenario tests whether your repository has the continuity agreements, shutdown planning, and financial diversification needed to ensure your holdings are preserved even if the repository itself cannot continue. The focus is on long-term sustainability, transition planning, and data preservation.

Cyberattack / Cybercrime

Your facility has been infiltrated and hostile actors have taken control of your cyberinfrastructure. All access to systems has been cut off. This could be a ransomware attack, a strategic intrusion for competitive or political reasons, or a physical attack in which hostile agents are present in your facility and disabling or accessing systems directly.

This scenario tests whether your repository can detect a breach, limit the damage, recover access to clean copies of your data, and restore operations. The focus is on data integrity, access controls, offline resilience, and recovery capability.

Loss of Personnel / Technical Expertise

The technical expertise needed to run your repository (such as knowledge of how to operate, maintain, and extend your software systems) is suddenly no longer available. This could happen through staff retirement or departure, the sudden discontinuation of a commercial vendor, or an open source project losing its maintainers.

This scenario tests whether that knowledge lives in your documentation and systems, or only in the minds of specific individuals. The focus is on knowledge documentation, staff cross-training, software accessibility, and whether your repository could continue operating if key people were no longer there.

Understanding Your Report

After completing the RCS, you will receive a report that summarizes your results and provides recommendations for improvement. This section explains what is in the report and how to read it.

How Scores Are Displayed

All scores in the report are displayed as percentages on a scale of 0 - 100%. Each score is assigned a maturity band with a color code to help you quickly understand where things stand:

Band	Score Range	What It Means
Critical	0-20%	Significant gaps across most practices; immediate action needed
Low	21-40%	Some practices in place but major gaps remain
Developing	41-60%	Foundational practices present but inconsistent or incomplete
Established	61-80%	Most practices in place, with some gaps remaining
Advanced	81-100%	Comprehensive and well-documented practices are in place.
Unknown	-	More than half the questions in this section were marked N/A. The score has been excluded from reporting as there was insufficient data to calculate a reliable result.

A higher score generally indicates that more resilience practices are in place. Scores should be interpreted in context and used to support self-evaluation, reflection, and planning. Even a high score may point to areas for continued improvement, and a low score can help identify where to focus next.

Part 1: Overall Resilience Summary

The Overall Resilience Summary gives you a quick overview of the repository's overall resilience. It includes:

- An overall resilience score and its maturity band, with a short plain-language interpretation of what the score means.
- Top 3 Strengths includes three sections where the repository is performing best.
- Top 3 Priority Areas include three sections with the most room for improvement.

Part 2: Crisis Scenario Readiness

This section of the report shows how the repository's current practices would hold up in each of the four crisis scenarios. For each scenario you will find a score, a maturity band, and a brief interpretation of what the score means in the context of that specific crisis.

A repository can have a strong overall score but a weak score for a specific scenario, and vice versa. These scores are useful for identifying specific vulnerabilities that the section-level view might not fully surface.

Part 3: Section Scores & Recommendations

This is the most detailed part of the report. For each of the seven sections you will find:

- The section score and maturity band.
- How many questions were answered and how many were marked N/A.
- A plain-language interpretation of what the score means for that section specifically.
- Two priority recommendations that include specific, actionable steps targeting the questions that scored lowest and have the broadest impact across crisis scenarios.

The recommendations are designed to be practical starting points. They are not exhaustive, and your team may identify additional steps based on your specific context. We encourage you to use the recommendations as a springboard for discussion rather than a checklist to complete in isolation.

How the Scores Are Calculated

This section explains the methodology behind the RCS scores for those who want to understand how the numbers are derived. The same methodology applies to both the online form and the spreadsheet version.

Section Scores

Each section receives a score from 0–100%. The score is calculated by adding up the numeric values of all answered questions in the section and dividing by the maximum possible score, which is five times the number of answered questions.

$$\text{Section Score} = (\text{Sum of answered question scores}) \div (\text{Number of answered questions} \times 5) \times 100$$

Questions marked N/A are excluded from scoring and not included in the numerator nor the denominator. This means N/A responses neither inflate nor deflate your score.

Important: If more than 50% of questions in a section are marked N/A, the section will be assigned a band of **Unknown**, and will be excluded from the overall resilience score. This threshold is applied per section.

Overall Resilience Score

The overall resilience score is a weighted average of your seven section scores, normalized to account for any sections marked **Unknown**. Each section is assigned a weight that reflects its relative importance to overall repository resilience. Sections marked **Unknown** are excluded from the calculation, and the remaining weights are adjusted proportionally so the score always reflects a fair comparison across the sections that were actually scored.

$$\text{Overall Score} = (\text{Sum of applicable section scores} \times \text{their weights}) \div (\text{Sum of weights of applicable sections}) \times 100$$

For example, if Section C is marked Unknown, its 5% weight is dropped and the remaining six section weights are used as the denominator, effectively rescaling the result to 100%.

Important: If the average number of questions answered across all sections falls below 50%, the overall resilience score and all crisis scenario scores will be marked as **Unknown**.

The section weights were determined based on the scope of each section and the directness of its relationship to crisis resilience. The table below summarizes the weights and the reasoning behind them:

Section	Weight	Rationale
A - Data Stewardship	20%	Data protection and documentation are the most foundational resilience practices. Without well-protected and well-documented data, no other practice can prevent permanent loss.
B - Infrastructure & Staffing	15%	Physical infrastructure and staffing resilience are core operational requirements that directly determine a repository's ability to maintain operations during a disruption.
C - Software	5%	Software resilience is important but software is generally more recoverable than lost data or failed infrastructure. This section's smaller scope and relative recoverability justify a lower weight.
D - Cybersecurity & Access Control	15%	Cyber threats are an active and growing risk with potentially immediate and irreversible consequences for data integrity and system availability.
E - Crisis Response & Recovery	20%	This section is the most directly relevant to the tool's core purpose and covers the broadest range of active crisis response and recovery capabilities.
F - Networks, Partnerships & Community	10%	External and internal relationships are important enablers of crisis response, but they are most effective when the practices in other sections are already strong.
G - Sustainability & Continuity	15%	Long-term viability and transition planning are critical to ensuring your repository's holdings survive beyond the life of the repository itself.

Crisis Scenario Scores

Each crisis scenario score is calculated using only the subset of questions identified as relevant to that scenario. These are called included questions. The same N/A exclusion logic applies (questions marked N/A among the included questions are excluded from both the numerator and denominator).

$$\text{Crisis Score} = (\text{Sum of included non-N/A question scores}) \div (\text{Number of included non-N/A questions} \times 5) \times 100$$

The full list of which questions are included in each crisis scenario is provided in Appendix A.

Note: If the overall resilience score is marked **Unknown** due to insufficient responses across all sections, all four crisis scenario scores will also be marked Unknown, as there is not enough data to calculate reliable scenario-level results.

Strength & Priority Rankings

The Top 3 Strengths and Top 3 Priority Areas in your Overall Resilience Summary are determined by ranking all scored sections using the following tiebreaking rules.

For Strengths, sections are ranked from highest to lowest using these rules in order:

- Higher raw section score ranks higher.
- If tied, higher section weight ranks higher.
- If still tied, fewer N/A responses ranks higher.
- If still tied, sections are ranked alphabetically by name.

For Priority Areas, sections are ranked from lowest to highest using these rules in order:

- Lower raw section score ranks higher.
- If tied, higher section weight ranks higher.
- If still tied, fewer N/A responses ranks higher.
- If still tied, sections are ranked alphabetically by name.

Question Priority Rankings Within Sections

The two priority recommendations shown for each section in Part 3 of your report are determined by ranking the questions within that section. Questions are ranked using the following rules in order:

- Lower question score ranks higher (more room for improvement).
- Higher scenario count ranks higher (the question impacts more crisis scenarios).
- Answered questions rank higher than questions marked N/A.
- Lower question ID number breaks any remaining ties.

Acknowledgements

The Repository Crisis Scorecards Version 2.0 builds on the foundation established by Joseph et. al. in the original RCS. That work was inspired by the need for practical, accessible tools for evaluating and planning for repository resilience, and was grounded in the [model data preservation rubric](#) developed by Schuster et al (2023).

Version 2.0 was developed with support from an award by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation to deepen our understanding of the resilience of data repositories and improve the tools used to assess it. Additional community responses and feedback gathered as part of that project directly informed the updates in this version.

We are grateful to everyone in the community who has completed the RCS, provided feedback, and contributed to the ongoing conversation about repository resilience.

If you would like to be a part of shaping the Repository Crisis Scorecards and/or writing papers on the topic of repository resiliency, please join the ESIP Sustainable Data Management Cluster on the first Monday of the month at 4pm Eastern Time or email us at esip-sustainabledm@lists.esipfed.org.

References

Schuster, D. C., Mayernik, M. S., Mullendore, G. L., and Marquis, J. W. (2023). What about Model Data? Best Practices for Preservation and Replicability. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, 104, E2053–E2064, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-22-0252.1>

Gum, J., & ESIP Sustainable Data Management Cluster. (2025). Repository Crisis Scorecards (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15122046>

How to Cite

If you use the Repository Crisis Scorecards in your work, please use the following citation format:

Sutton-Kennedy, T., & ESIP Sustainable Data Management Cluster. (2026). Repository Crisis Scorecards (Version 2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20451149>

For citation of the original Version 1.0, please refer to the Acknowledgments section.

Changelog

Version	Date	Summary of Changes
2.0	2026-05-29	Major revision informed by community feedback and supported by an Alfred P. Sloan Foundation award. Key updates include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> revised and expanded question set with guidance text added to each question to support consistent interpretation standardized Likert scale (1–5) applied consistently across all questions N/A response option added to all questions with normalized scoring that excludes non-applicable responses scores normalized to a 0–100% scale for easier interpretation automated report added Added online form version, and updated the Google Sheets, Excel Spreadsheet (.xlsx), Word (.docx), and PDF versions.
1.03	2026-02-06	Added notetaking/document version of the scorecards as pdf and docx
1.02	2025-04-15	Minor update addressing bugs and content refinements identified after initial release: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Corrected spelling errors throughout. Updated and corrected links in the RCS Instructions document. Updated the DOI to always point to the most recent version on Zenodo. Fixed conditional color formatting in the Repository Resilience Scorecard Tidied scoring formulas. Added Service Level Agreements guidance to the RRS. Revised question wording for three items in the Data Impact and Recovery Scorecard (DIRS): FAIR Compliance, CARE Compliance and Ethical Usage Considerations, and Third Party Application Support Through Transition.
1.01	2025-04-10	Fixed conditional color formatting for some cells in RRS
1.0	2025-04-03	Initial release

Appendix A: Crisis Scenario Question Assignments

The table below lists all 42 RCS questions and indicates which of the four crisis scenarios each question contributes to. A checkmark (✓) means the question is included in that scenario's score calculation. Questions with no checkmarks (A9, A10) are scored in the section score but are not mapped to any specific crisis scenario.

#	Question Topic	Natural Disaster	Defunding	Cyberattack	Loss of Expertise
A1	National replication	✓	✓	✓	
A2	International replication	✓	✓	✓	
A3	Offline or air-gapped copies	✓	✓	✓	
A4	Storage media diversity	✓		✓	
A5	External replication by others	✓	✓	✓	
A6	Metadata completeness		✓		✓
A7	FAIR compliance		✓		✓
A8	Data management plans		✓		✓
A9	Ethical considerations				
A10	Dataset deprecation process				
B1	Physical infrastructure	✓			
B2	Staff cross-training and coverage	✓	✓	✓	✓
B3	Leadership succession planning		✓	✓	✓
B4	Staff training and development				✓
B5	Backup schedule and testing	✓	✓	✓	
B6	Vendor and supply chain risk	✓	✓	✓	
C1	Data accessibility		✓		✓
C2	Software licensing and maintenance		✓		✓
C3	Technical installation documentation		✓	✓	✓
D1	Activity logging and monitoring			✓	
D2	Access controls			✓	
D3	Cybersecurity expertise			✓	

E1	Remote work capability	✓	✓	✓	
E2	Electronic data transfer capability	✓	✓	✓	
E3	Physical data transfer capability	✓	✓		
E4	Disaster recovery planning	✓	✓	✓	✓
E5	Software redeployment readiness	✓	✓	✓	✓
E6	Internal crisis communication	✓	✓	✓	✓
E7	Public disruption notices	✓	✓	✓	✓
E8	Downstream dependency mapping	✓	✓	✓	✓
E9	Third-party application continuity	✓	✓	✓	✓
E10	User access continuity	✓	✓	✓	✓
E11	Dataset recovery prioritization	✓	✓	✓	✓
F1	Data replication and archival agreements	✓	✓	✓	
F2	Operational support agreements	✓	✓	✓	✓
F3	Community and stakeholder engagement		✓		
G1	Data and systems migration planning		✓		
G2	Shutdown and data transfer planning		✓		✓
G3	National continuity agreement		✓		✓
G4	International continuity agreement		✓		
G5	Parent institution continuity planning		✓		
G6	Funding diversity		✓		